

E-marketing of Bollywood Movies (A Case Study of Movies With Net Earning Above INR 100 Crore)

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ABSTRACT

The Hindi film industry of India a.k.a. Bollywood is the world's largest film producer. It produces close to 1000 movies a year. For that approximately 14 million viewers swarm the theaters each day and it sold more than four billion cinema tickets every year. According to FICCI-KPMG Indian Media and Entertainment Industry Report 2013 the Indian film industry is projected to grow at a CAGR of 11.5 percent to touch INR 193.3 Billion in 2017. The growth of Indian film industry in 2012 over 2011 is 21 % and the estimated size of film industry in 2013 would be 122.4 INR billion. With the growing competition on domestic as well international market Bollywood has started to spend a fortune towards movie marketing in order to drive the business.

Film marketing activities have progressed beyond posters and promos with the aggressive use of new marketing tools like social media, portals, search engines and mobile devices. Use of social media has become an important component of pre-release marketing strategy for any movie. The recent trend is to develop mobile apps for promotion of movies. For instance, Disney UTV's marketing team developed a mobile app for movie 'Barfi' which was used to create a strong connect between the central character and the audience.

In 2012, the average film marketing costs ranged anywhere between INR 80-120 million. For high budget films, this went up to INR 150 million and for low budget films, in some cases, it exceeded their production cost. As per industry estimates, for a low budget film, a minimum budget of INR 35 to 50 million is required to ensure a decent commercial release for the film. It is anticipated that as media clutter grows, marketing budgets for films will continue to climb in order for products to get noticed.

Introduction

Film marketing is evolving into a growing industry in India. Over the years we have seen a seamless integration of marketing

ideas selling the film and being responsible for its success. Earlier the film's director and the banner were good enough to draw the audiences, but now the moviegoers want novelty and more

than banner and star-cast to watch a movie. The hype and hoopla created by the film marketers goes down a long way in predicting the film's success. More and more filmmakers are adopting out-of-box strategies to cut through the clutter in the highly competitive business. There is a new breed of filmmakers and production houses who want to ensure the highest possibility of making a movie a hit and get maximum footfalls. It is very important to communicate the USP of a movie to the viewers in a more interesting way.

Earlier the barometer of success was the number of days a movie runs on a theatre. Those were the era of the Silver Jubilee, Golden Jubilee, Diamond Jubilee, but now it's all the matter of the first week. Today films have been released with as high as 3000 prints worldwide and the collection of weekend decides the fate of the movie. Under these circumstances, marketing is the key to ensure a big opening and to draw audiences to the theatres.

A new breed of consumer has evolved with India's growing young population. There media consumption habits and preferences for niche content is driving marketers to provide innovative and direct platforms to get in touch with the audience. Around 81 per cent of the online Indian population, according to a report by **Hungama Digital Media**, engages in some kind of social interactivity on the web, making it an ideal place for the film marketers draw young

crowds. **Jyoti Deshpande, Chief Operating Officer and Commercial Director, Eros International**, says: "Internet viral marketing is less about how much you spend and more about how effectively you spend." Today it's almost a norm to launch the website as well Facebook fan page of a movie simultaneously. Promoting movies through social networking sites such as Facebook, blogs like blogger and micro-blogging sites like twitter etc. helps to build a reputation, create real time conversations, connect and at the same time engage the target audiences in the online world.

The Bollywood 100 Crore Club

(billion)

Year	Film	No. of Days	Net Gross
2008	Ghajini	18	1.15
2009	3 idiots	9	2.02
2010	Dabangg	8	1.40
2010	Golmaal 3	17	1.08
2011	Ready	14	1.21
2011	Singham	37	1.00
2011	Bodyguard	7	1.41
2011	Ra.One	11	1.15
2011	Don 2	16	1.15
2012	Agneepath	11	1.20
2012	Housefull 2	9	1.12

2012	Rowdy Rathore	10	1.33
2012	Bol Bachchan	20	1.00
2012	Ek tha Tiger	5	1.86
2012	Barfi	19	1.20
2012	Jab tak hai Jaan	17	1.21
2012	Son of Sardar	16	1.05
2012	Dabangg 2	6	1.55
2013	Race 2	14	1.02

Source: * http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bollywood_100_Crore_Club

Objective of The Study

The present paper is an attempt to understand the confluence of “New Media”, (the term specifically used for the Internet and related platform to access content on demand) and one of the oldest and most loved forms of entertainment i.e. cinema. The driving force to carry out this research was the simple question, i.e. “How e-marketing is affecting the revenue and success of contemporary Bollywood movies”.

1. To Study the 4P’s of the movie marketing
2. To analyze the importance of marketing in promoting movies
3. To know the impact of movie promotion on the viewers
4. To find out the effect of e-marketing strategies on the viewers

Research Design

For the purpose of the study the paper has been divided into the following stages:

a) Review Of Literature

The idea of effectively presenting the unique selling point of a film to the online audience and the dynamics that influence the same creates an interesting proposition. *The methodology employed for researching on this subject comprised of literature review of following reports :*

- *FICCI-KPMG Indian Media and Entertainment Industry Report 2013*
- *12th Five Year Plan (2012-2017): Report of the working group on Information and Broadcasting Sector*
- *Digital Advertising in India, 2013, IMAI Report*

These reports were studied and reviewed thoroughly. This literature review formed the basis of the research paper. Further, due to unavailability of adequate data related to the marketing expenses of Bollywood movies with respect to the expenses on conventional and unconventional media, a case study approach was resorted wherein the marketing campaigns of those movies were studied whose net collection in domestic market was more than INR 100 Crore. The case study approach helped to understand the fine line which divides the conventional media/methods from the unconventional ones.

b) Research Analysis

The content of the websites and messages given on various social networking sites has been observed and analyzed in order to get the required data. Qualitative content analysis was conducted as per the need of the study. Content analysis is a methodology by which the researcher seeks to determine the content of written, spoken or published communication by systematic objective and quantitative analysis.

c) Expert Group Analysis

To make deep understanding about e-Marketing of Bollywood movies, an experience survey has been done by asking questions to the experts. The researcher identified and interviewed experts including new media teachers and industry people who are working in the same area.

d) User Survey

A survey has been conducted through purposive sampling technique to add the audience perspective into the study. The researcher has selected 50 people about their habit of new media consumption related to promotion of Bollywood movies. The use of Facebook fan pages, YouTube official channel and following the tweets of starcast and directors are taken into consideration. These 50 people include students, office goers, and housewives within the age group of 16 to 30.

Major Findings

The Bollywood has an interesting proposition of success. On one hand the big budget, big star & the big banner movie continue to be the ultimate success formula at box office, like 3 idiots, Ek Tha Tiger, Dabangg 2 etc. But on the flip side films which are based on strong content (storyline), small budgets and non-star with aggressive marketing and distribution strategy are also creating big bucks.

Mr. Kamal Jain, Group CFO-India, Eros International Media Ltd. points out that "Vicky Donor and English Vinglish, illustrated new trend that smaller budget, high concept films can achieve higher returns at the box office and other channels of distribution, provided they are marketed and distributed like big high profile films.

In 2008, Ghajini became the first movie to cross INR 1 billion at the box office, setting a new benchmark for Bollywood. However, its exclusivity seems to be fading with an increasing number of films crossing the INR 1 billion threshold. 2012 witnessed nine films crossing the coveted INR 1 billion mark, as compared to only five films in 2011. Moreover, with box office collection of 'Ek Tha Tiger' touching close to INR 2 billion, aspirations have been set higher. Continued success at the box office driven by strong content and expansion of multiplexes is expected to establish INR 2 billion as the new benchmark for success.

Bollywood : INR 1 billion club

Number of movies crossing INR 1 billion

Source : KPMG in India analysis.

In India social media constitute about 25 percent of the internet surfing time, and has more than 70 million social networks surfers. Such a potential platform is rather hard to ignore for digital marketing. These consumers are already being targeted by the film industry. The current spend on digital marketing platforms such as Facebook and YouTube is approximately INR 1.8 million and will rise significantly in the near future.

For example, Yash Chopra's Jab Tak Hai Jaan trailer received 30,000 likes in the first week of its release on YouTube, breaking records worldwide#. Movies such as Anurag Kashyap's Gangs of Wasseypur utilized social media very effectively to create attention. The sequel was marketed through a pseudo election campaign between the sequel's prime characters. The election was staged on Twitter. Similarly a digital app was created for movie Barfi on YouTube (www.youtube.com/barfi) where people

could make Ranbir Kapoor dance, smile, cry and do anything else they desired. They could also learn tips to impress girls at Barfi's Pataoshala. The app was a viral hit gaining over 250,000 users in 2 weeks and was hailed by the Google India team as the best online innovation that has been done on YouTube in the past 1.5 years. The app also won a bronze in the video innovation category at the prestigious Yahoo Big Idea Chair Awards.

Source: *Facebook has 71 million active users in India, 50 million duplicate accounts worldwide, gadgets.ndtv.com, Feb 2013

<http://www.indiatimes.com/bollywood/jab-tak-hai-jaan-trailer-creates-history-44110.html>

Discussions

Mr. Sanjay Gaikwad, CEO & Managing Director, UFO Moviez India Ltd., emphasizes that "The technology is impacting the way media is made, distributed and monetized. Consumer lifestyles have become increasingly busy with time. This has given rise to a need to consume media on-demand as and where one's lifestyle allows". This goes well with the marketers who are innovating on their e-marketing strategy to engage audience.

Taking into account multiple users for a single wire-line connection, the number of internet users reached 174 million in 2012, about 25 percent of the size of the

total TV viewers in the country and is expected to reach over 60 percent of total TV viewers by 2017. There were approximately 38 million Smartphones with active Internet connections in India at the end of 2012.*

Shailja Gupta, US country head of production house Red Chillies Entertainment says, "Films seldom generate revenue from digital marketing, but it helps them to tie up with brands to create co-branded promotions, which in turn saves a lot of money for the producers and distributors".

The e-marketing strategy of Bollywood films ensures two-way communication with the audience. For this, specific content is developed for the internet. Film-makers are collaborating with online portals to sell movie-related merchandise. Mydala.com, an Indian social commerce and marketing platform, tied up with UTV Motion Pictures as a marketing partner for Barfi. As part of the association, the portal ran a promotional campaign on its website as well as social media outlets like Facebook, Twitter and Google+.

Shikha Kapur, Executive Director Marketing, Studios, Disney UTV says that "In film marketing the battle for eyeballs can be won or lost in the first 2 weeks of the campaign. First impressions are critical in our industry, so once our research on pre-campaign audience awareness is done, we ensure that our

first creative (trailer and posters) has very high on appeal and reach amongst our target audience. Once a good base is created then further marketing interventions in the 6-8 week period prior to the film's release, become that much more effective in achieving box office revenue targets".

Source: *KPMG in India Analysis

Survey

- Researcher has selected 50 people to understand their use of social networking sites Facebook, YouTube and Twitter. These 50 people include students, office goers, and housewives within the age group of 16 to 35.
- Study shows that the research group in general spend 2-3 hours a day on social networking sites, but it varies according to the age group.
- The survey revealed that 48% people were active participants in the Facebook Movie Page. The nature of discussion was mainly about the personal likes and dislikes of users and comment on the performances of star-cast and directors etc. Around 75% of users have watched the promotional trailer on YouTube and less than 40% were following the tweets of actors and director of the movie.
- The study revealed that overall 70% people found the new media as an effective way for the success of movie marketing, 17% people did not think

it as an effective tool while the rest did not say anything on the issue.

Conclusion

It has been observed that movie marketing in India is becoming more innovative and spreading its wings into new unexplored dimensions. Besides the conventional poster and promo campaign, which was one-way communication now the norms are changing to be more interactive. Industry data suggests that around 30 to 40 percent of total marketing budget of a movie is assigned for e-marketing. It could be a Social Media fan page, official YouTube page, Tweets of actor, director, producer and well written blog to promote the movie. The idea is to engage the audience into the steps of making and promoting of movies. With the first shot to movie release, there are several steps of developments like releasing the music of the film, promotional events of star cast, on air promos etc. are kept posting by the marketers on Facebook, YouTube and Twitter, to generate curiosity about the movie. A large section of youth is indulge in social media and its easy to catch their attention. Though the e-marketing strategy are not meant to directly transform into revenues but somehow they serve the larger purpose. Merchandise related to movie contributes a significant amount of revenue and can be sold easily through these online promotions.

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